

A New Strategy for the α -Vinylolation of Ketones : Application to an Enantioselective Synthesis of Sesquiterpene (+)- α -Elemene[†]

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A new, simple and preparatively useful protocol for the construction of α -vinyl ketones, particularly those bearing a quaternary carbon centre, from the corresponding alkenes has been devised. Our four-step strategy consists of dichloroketene addition, base catalysed ring contraction to 'push-pull' cyclopropane esters, reduction and eliminative cyclopropane fragmentation to unravel the α -vinyl ketone moiety. The generality of this approach has been demonstrated with a few representative olefins and good regio- and stereocontrol has been observed. As an application of this methodology, an enantioselective synthesis of sesquiterpene hydrocarbon (+)- α -elemene (42) from *R*-(+)-limonene (43) has been accomplished.

Among natural products, terpenes occupy a special position on account of their widespread occurrence and the bewildering array of carbocyclic skeleta that they embody. They exhibit biological responses and activities ranging from flavours for drinks, fragrances in perfumes, sex-attractants, insecticides and even as anticancer compounds. Terpenes are also notable for certain structural motifs that are invariably present in them, as a consequence of the mevalonate based biosynthetic pathway through which they are derived. For example, *gem*-dimethyl groups, quaternary carbon cen-

tres with angular methyl group(s), spiro-fused carbon centres, trisubstituted olefinic bonds and vinyl groups at quaternary carbon centres are extensively present among terpenes. Thus, besides carbocyclic ring construction, appropriate placement of some of these structural motifs along with requisite functionalities is an intrinsic part of terpene synthesis. It is not surprising, therefore, that considerable effort has been directed towards developing protocols for generating structural motifs characteristic of terpenes¹.

As part of an ongoing research programme in the area of terpene synthesis, our attention and interest was drawn to the extensive occurrence of the structural moiety 1 among many terpenes. In Scheme 1^{2a-f} are displayed selected examples from mono-, mero-, sesqui-, di- and triterpenes, as well as terpenic alkaloids wherein, the moiety 1 is present. While the quaternary carbon centre bearing moiety 1 is important in its own right, we further recognised that a more embellished sub-structure 2 containing an α -vinyl ketone moiety is even better in terms of synthetic utility, as this

functionality could be elaborated and modified through well known reactions/transformations into a variety of structural fragments present in terpenic natural products. Some of the more promising elaborations of 2 are depicted in Scheme 2. Thus, the presence of sub-structure 1 in many natural products and the various possibilities of elaborating 2 into diverse terpene skeleta became the twin motivating factors for us to consider the development of *de novo* methodology for rapidly and efficiently accessing these two moieties.

Despite the widespread occurrence of the structural moieties 1 and 2 among terpenes and other related natural products, methodologies available in the literature for accessing them are rather limited³. Particularly, the generation of α -vinyl ketone moiety 2 from a carbonyl precursor via α -vinylation presents considerable difficulties. While vinyl anion species are well documented, α -vinylation of ketones requires access to a vinyl cation equivalent (Scheme 3). Efforts in recent years have been directed towards generating vinyl cation synthons with some degree of success³. Alternately, classical methods of α -substitution with vinyl group surrogate and further functional group modifications have also been explored (Scheme 3).

The various strategies described in the literature for generating the α -vinyl ketone moiety have their own disadvantages in terms of regio- and stereochemical intricacies. Most of the earlier routes to 2 have emanated from a carbonyl precursor with manoeuvring at the α -pro nucleophilic centre. However, it is well recognised that in such operations, regiochemical control invariably presents some problems. In some cases, the reagents employed for the purpose are either very expensive or have to be acquired through tedious, multi-step sequence. The success achieved so far in the stereoselective introduction of the vinyl group onto a quaternary carbon centre is rather limited. Thus, the genera-

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tion of a quaternary centre, with methyl and vinyl groups adjacent to carbonyl group with regio- and stereochemical control continues to be a demanding proposition and there is need for newer, simpler and practical solutions^{4,5}.

α-Vinyl ketone moiety via dichloroketene adducts and 'push-pull' cyclopropanes: As already mentioned, the wide ranging applications of functional moieties 1 and 2, particularly the latter, required that these be accessed in short, reliable, regio- and stereoselective sequences from readily available starting materials. In this context, it was felt that employing an olefinic precursor, rather than the usually employed carbonyl precursor, for generating the *α*-vinyl ketone moiety 2 could be a better proposition. Towards this end, our attention was drawn to some reports of interesting transformations of the [2+2]-cycloadducts of dichloroketene and olefins⁶. It has been reported in the literature that *α,α*-dichlorocyclobutanones, on exposure to base, undergo Haller-Bauer type of ring cleavage⁷ to furnish the corresponding ring-opened dichloro esters. While many such cleavage reactions have been recorded, Fletcher and Hassner⁸ reported an interesting deviation from this trend. They found that the dichloroketene adduct 3 of 2-cholestene, on treatment with excess of sodium methoxide in methanol, afforded an epimeric mixture of cyclopropyl methyl esters 4a,b, in almost quantitative yields (Scheme 4). We were greatly attracted by this observation, through which functionalised cyclopropyl esters with 'push-pull' type of substitution pattern could be readily obtained. We recognised that the ester group in these 'push-pull' cyclopropanes like 4a,b could be elaborated to a carbinol group, which on activation should readily fragment⁹ to furnish the *α*-vinyl ketone moiety. Through this logic, outline of a strategy for the generation

of *α*-vinyl ketone moiety, with or without a quaternary carbon centre, from an olefin emerged. This is shown in Scheme 5. The steps involved would be (i) olefin-dichloroketene 5 → 6 [2+2]-cycloaddition, (ii) methoxide mediated ring contraction to a cyclopropane ester 6 → 7, (iii) reduction of the ester functionality to a cyclopropyl carbinol moiety 7 → 8 and (iv) activation of the carbinol hydroxyl group and

Scheme 4. Reagents : (a) NaOMe, MeOH, Δ , quant.

cyclopropyl fragmentation to generate the α -vinyl ketone moiety **9** (Scheme 5). Thus, we ventured to explore the feasibility and generality of Scheme 5 to gain entry into α -vinyl ketone moiety from olefinic precursors.

At this stage, we also reasoned that implementation of Scheme 5, in actuality means homologation of an olefin by two carbon atoms in the form of a vinyl group with concomitant generation of a carbonyl functionality. Thus, if C_{10} -monoterpene hydrocarbons were to be employed as precursors, homologated C_{12} -entities bearing a α -vinyl ketone functionality would result. The functionality present in these C_{12} -homo-monoterpenes has the potential for further manipulation with amplification of carbon content as indicated earlier in Scheme 2. Thus, monoterpenes can be employed for the synthesis of higher terpenes, particularly sesquiterpenes¹⁰.

To implement the theme depicted in Scheme 5 and to demonstrate its versatility, we selected 1-methylcyclohexene (**10**), 1-phenylcyclohexene (**11**), 1-methylcyclopentene (**12**), 1,5-cycloocta-diene (**13**), (+)- Δ^3 -carene (**14**) and (-)- α -pinene (**15**) as the precursor olefins. All the six olefins (**10-15**) were routinely transformed into their α,α -dichloroketene adducts (**16-21**) respectively (Scheme 6). The method of choice for this purpose involved trichloroacetyl chloride and off-the-shelf zinc dust in the presence of ultrasound irradiation¹¹. Under these conditions, cleaner products were realised and reaction times were considerably shortened. All the ketene adducts (**16-21**) were duly characterised on the basis of their spectral characteristics.

The ketene adducts (**16-21**) were subjected to the ring-contraction-rearrangement protocol. Treatment of the cycloadducts with excess of sodium methoxide in methanol under reflux, furnished the corresponding cyclopropyl esters (**22a,b-27a,b**) as diastereomeric mixtures in good yields

(60–80%). This was a pleasing outcome and set the stage for the next key step. Although the mixture of the esters **22a,b-27a,b** could be separated for the sake of characterisation, the stereostructures to the individual compounds could not be assigned unambiguously based on the spectral

Scheme 5

data. The chemical shift changes were too small for a clear cut distinction. However, for the contemplated sequence, it was not considered necessary to separate the diastereomers. Therefore, the mixture of diastereomeric cyclopropyl esters (**22a,b-27a,b**) was carried as such for the next step.

The next key operation in this sequence was to set up the cyclopropylcarbinyl-homoallylic rearrangement in the activated 'push-pull' cyclopropyl carbinol derivatives⁹. For this purpose, the ester moiety in **22a,b-27a,b** was reduced using DIBAL-H at low temperatures, to furnish the corresponding cyclopropyl carbinols **28-33** respectively, as diastereomeric mixtures. Having obtained the required cyclopropyl carbinols **28-33**, the objective now was to implement the fragmentation sequence⁹ to access the desired α -

Scheme 6. Reagents, condition and yields: (a) CCl_3COCl , Zn, Et_2O , (b) NaOMe 5 eq., MeOH, Δ , 10–30 min, (c) DIBAL-H, DCM, -78° , 20–60 min, (d) MsCl 1.2 eq., Py, 0° R.T., 15 min; 35% HClO_4 , Et_2O , 0° , 30 min (E = COOMe and X = CH_2OH).

vinyl ketones by activating the hydroxyl group. To execute this protocol, carbinols **28–33** were reacted with methanesulfonyl chloride to obtain the corresponding 'push-pull' mesylates. Not surprisingly, the mesylates were not isolated but instead we directly obtained the α -vinyl ketones **34–39** respectively (Scheme 6). However, the α -vinyl ketones (**34–39**) were sometimes found to be contaminated with the enol ethers **41** formed concomitantly during the reaction of carbinols or iodide **40** (X = OH, I, etc.) with methanesulfonyl chloride or a halogenation reagent (Scheme 7). Therefore, the reaction product obtained from the mesylation reaction was briefly exposed to aq. perchloric acid (to hydrolyse the enol ether) and α -vinyl ketones **34–39** were isolated in good yield (40–75%). All the α -vinyl ketones obtained (Scheme 6) were duly characterised.

*First enantioselective synthesis of (+)- α -elemene **42**¹² :*

The simple and short protocol for the synthesis of α -vinyl ketones from olefins prompted us to seek further ap-

plications in the synthesis of terpenes, particularly those bearing a quaternary carbon centre. The high regio- and stereoselectivities in the addition of the dichloroketene was expected to influence the stereochemical outcome of the α -vinyl ketone formation and pave the way for the enantioselective synthesis of various carbocyclic skeleta starting from the monoterpene chiral pool. In this pursuit, the elemene group of sesquiterpenes (Scheme 8)¹³ with the vinyl and the methyl groups strategically placed at the quaternary cen-

Scheme 7

tre, attracted our immediate attention.

(+)- α -Elemene (**42**), a sesquiterpene hydrocarbon, was first isolated by Ivanov¹⁴ from the oil of *Bulgarian zdravets*. The structural evidence for (+)- α -elemene (**42**), the main product obtained in the dehydration of elemol, was provided by Paknikar and Bhattacharya¹⁵, on the basis of degradative

and NMR studies. However, this data was not good enough to differentiate between the two possible isomeric structures for this hydrocarbon. To clarify, we employed incisive NOESY studies and settled the structure of **42** unambiguously, which proved the correctness of the earlier assignment. In 1977, Vig and co-workers¹⁶ reported the synthesis of racemic α -elemene. However, the enantioselective synthesis of (+)- α -elemene (**42**) has not been reported in the literature and in this paper we report first such accomplishment¹².

For our projected synthesis, the readily available chiral monoterpene *R*-(+)-limonene (**43**) with pre-installed isopropyl and methyl groups in 1,4-relationship, as present in the elemene group of sesquiterpenes, was selected as a cheap and abundantly available starting material. Through the recognition of structural patterns present in limonene and the target structure **42**, and keeping in mind our two carbon methodology for generating the α -vinyl ketone moiety, a retrosynthetic strategy could be formulated as shown in Scheme 9.

The α -vinyl ketone (**48**) and the enone (**49**) were identified as the advanced intermediates for the synthesis of (+)- α -elemene. To execute the synthetic plan revealed through

the retrosynthetic analysis, *R*-(+)-limonene (**43**) was regioselectively hydrogenated over platinum oxide to furnish the desired *R*-(+)-dihydrolimonene (**44**) in 90% yield¹⁷. The reaction of olefin **44** with α,α -dichloroketene (*vide supra*) proceeded smoothly and stereoselectively to furnish the expected [2+2]-adduct (**45**) in 65% yield (Scheme 10). It was reasonable to assume on the basis of previous precedences that the ketene addition to the trisubstituted double bond had occurred from the face opposite to the isopropyl group. Having acquired the cycloadduct (**45**) in good quantities, our next objective was to carry out the ring contraction-rearrangement protocol to obtain the cyclopropyl esters **46a,b**. Exposure of the ketene adduct **45** to the sodium methoxide-methanol milieu yielded a diastereomeric mixture of 'push-pull' cyclopropyl esters **46a,b** in 75% (Scheme 10). At this stage, the mixture was not required to be separated and the same was carried over to the reduction-step. However, the mixture was separated for characterisation purpose, and each diastereomer was found to be in agreement

with its gross formulation.

The mixture of the ester (**46a,b**) on reduction with DIBAL-H, furnished a diastereomeric mixture of bicyclic cyclopropyl carbinols (**47a,b**) in 80% yield (Scheme 10). However, reduction of the ester mixture (**46a,b**) with LAH was found to be more efficient, especially for large-scale preparation. The crude carbinol mixture (**47a,b**) was directly subjected to the key ring-opening reaction to generate the α -vinyl ketone moiety. Brief exposure of **47a,b** to methanesulfonyl chloride and pyridine followed by aq. HClO₄ treatment resulted in the facile ring opening via the cyclopropylcarbinyl-homoallylic rearrangement to furnish the α -vinyl ketone (**48**) as a single diastereomer in 78% yield (Scheme 10). Subsequently, we have found that the **47** \rightarrow **48** transformation involving cyclopropyl cleavage can be carried out more efficiently (90% yield) on exposure to *in situ* generated trimethylsilyl iodide¹⁸ (TMSI). In this way, further treatment with aq. perchloric acid was not required as the intermediate enol ether, if formed, was also cleaved by TMSI.

For elaboration to the elemene skeleton, a C₃-unit had to be added to the carbonyl group of C₁₂-ketone **48**. For this purpose, addition of isopropyllithium and isopropyl-

Scheme 10. *Reagents, condition and yields*: (a) H_2/PtO_2 , EtOH, 90%, (b) CCl_3COCl , Zn, Et_2O , sonication, 65%, (c) NaOMe-MeOH, Δ , 75%, (d) DIBAL-H, DCM, -40° , 80% or LAH, Et_2O , R.T.; 75%, (e) MsCl, Py, 0° , R.T.; 15 min, 35% aq. HClO_4 , ether, 0° , 30 min, 78%, (f) Me_3SiI , MeCN, R.T., 90%, (g) SeO_2 , Bu^tOH , Δ , 45%, (h) 2-propyllithium, THF, ultrasound. (i) *p*-TsCl, CHCl_3 , R.T., 42% from 49.

lithium to **48** was attempted. However, the ketone **48** was found to be quite unreactive. The sluggish reactivity of the ketone **48** could be attributed to the steric hindrance by the isopropyl group and the quaternary carbon bearing the vinyl group on both the faces of the carbonyl group. To circumvent this problem, it was decided to transform the ketone **48** into the enone **49**. The carbonyl group of the enone **49** was expected to project outwards with the introduction of the unsaturation in the ring system and thus partially relieve the steric hindrance caused by the neighbouring isopropyl substituent. After considerable trial and error, it was found that, dehydrogenation of the α -vinyl ketone **48** with selenium dioxide in *t*-butanol delivered the required enone **49** in 45% yield (Scheme 10). Having acquired the enone **49**, our next objective was to effect appropriate 1,2-nucleophilic addition on the carbonyl group of the enone moiety. Treatment of the enone **49** with isopropyl lithium in THF, under ultrasound irradiation, furnished a diastereomeric mixture of the carbinols **50**. In **50**, with all its carbon atoms placed in requisite positions, functional group fine-tuning was sought to accomplish the total synthesis of (+)- α -elemene (**42**). A dehydration reaction was, therefore, executed on the alcohol mixture **50** and was found to be very facile. Exposure of the carbinol mixture **50** to *p*-toluenesulfonyl chloride delivered (+)- α -elemene (**42**) in 42% yield (Scheme 10). The spectral data (uv, ir, ^1H , ^{13}C nmr) of **42** were found to be in full agreement with its formulation as

well as with the reported data¹⁵ for the natural product. The specific rotation of the synthetic sample obtained by us ($[\alpha]_D = +112.5^\circ$) matches with that of the natural product ($[\alpha]_D = +116^\circ$)¹⁵ and supports the absolute configuration assigned earlier to (+)- α -elemene (**42**).

In short, we have outlined a short, simple and general protocol for the elaboration of alkenes to α -vinylketones in a regio- and stereoselective manner. In a specific application of this methodology, the first total synthesis of the sesquiterpene hydrocarbon (+)- α -elemene has been accomplished. Several other applications of this approach have also been disclosed by us¹⁹.

Experimental

General procedure for dichloroketene additions to the olefins (10-15): A dry nitrogen filled 100 ml three-necked RB flask fitted with a nitrogen inlet and pressure equalising addition funnel was charged with olefin (5 mmol), zinc dust (10 mmol) and anhydrous ether (50 ml). The flask was then partially submerged in a sonicator water-bath in a place that produced maximum agitation to the suspension and freshly distilled trichloroacetyl chloride (7.5 mmol) in anhydrous ether (25 ml) was added during a 30 min period. Sonication was continued at $15-20^\circ$ and the reaction was usually complete within 1 h. After quenching with wet ether, the reaction mixture was filtered through celite and the filtrate was washed with water (2×20 ml), saturated sodium bicarbonate (2×20 ml) and brine solution (20 ml). The ethereal solu-

tion was dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and the solvent was evaporated. Purification of the crude product was effected by chromatography over a short column of silica gel and vacuum distillation.

8,8-Dichloro-1-methylbicyclo[4.2.0]octan-7-one (16) : Reaction of 1-methylcyclohexene (**10**; 1.9 g, 20.0 mmol), zinc dust (2.6 g, 40.0 mmol) and trichloroacetyl chloride (3.4 ml, 30.0 mmol) afforded the dichloroketene adduct (**16**; 3.3 g, 80%) after bulb-to-bulb distillation : b.p. 60°/0.14 mm; ν_{\max} (neat) 2900, 2840, 1790, 1440 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 3.60–3.50 (1H, m, O=C–CH), 2.20–1.00 (8H, m, 1.49 (3H, s, –C–CH₃)).

8,8-Dichloro-1-phenylbicyclo[4.2.0]octan-7-one (17) : Reaction of 1-phenylcyclohexene (**11**; 3.2 g, 20.0 mmol), zinc dust (2.6 g, 40.0 mmol) and trichloroacetyl chloride (3.4 ml, 30.0 mmol) afforded the dichloroketene adduct (**17**; 3.2 g, 60%) : b.p. 150°/0.1 mm; ν_{\max} (neat) 3061, 3030, 1805, 1603, 1497, 1449 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 7.50–7.20 (5H, m, ArH), 4.20–4.10 (1H, m, O=C–CH), 2.40–2.10 (2H, m), 2.00–0.80 (6H, m).

7,7-Dichloro-1-methylbicyclo[3.2.0]heptan-6-one (18) : Reaction of 1-methylcyclopentene (**12**; 2.0 g, 24.0 mmol), zinc dust (3.2 g, 48.0 mmol) and trichloroacetyl chloride (4 ml, 36 mmol) afforded the dichloroketene adduct (**18**; 3.29 g, 70%) after bulb-to-bulb distillation : b.p. 100°/0.2 mm; ν_{\max} (neat) 2950, 2850, 1790, 800 cm^{-1} .

10,10-Dichlorobicyclo[6.2.0]dec-4-ene-9-one (19) : Reaction of 1,5-cyclooctadiene (**13**; 500 mg, 4.62 mmol), zinc dust (600 mg, 9.17 mmol) and trichloroacetyl chloride (0.78 ml, 7.0 mmol) afforded the dichloroketene adduct (**19**; 1.16 g, 70%) after bulb-to-bulb distillation : b.p. 110°/0.1 mm; ν_{\max} (neat) 1805 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 5.64 (2H, br s, –CH=CH–), 3.88–3.52 (1H, m, Cl₂C–CH–), 3.20–2.80 (1H, m, O=C–CH–), 2.60–1.80 (8H, m); ^{13}C nmr δ (25.0 MHz) 196.7, 130.3, 129.9, 88.0, 58.6, 49.7, 24.2, 25.1, 24.1.

(–)-(1S,3S,5R,7R)-9,9-Dichloro-1,4,4-trimethyltricyclo[5.2.0.0^{3,5}]nonan-8-one (**20**) : Reaction of (+)- Δ^3 -carene (**14**; 2.0 g, 14.7 mmol), zinc dust (1.9 g, 29.4 mmol) and trichloroacetyl chloride (2.5 ml, 22.0 mmol) afforded the dichloroketene adduct (**20**; 2.4 g, 68%) after bulb-to-bulb distillation : b.p. 120°/0.2 mm; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} -80.43^\circ$ (c, 5.59; CHCl₃); ν_{\max} (neat) 2900, 2850, 1790, 1455, 870 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 3.36 (1H, t, *J* 4.0 Hz, O=C–CH), 2.50–2.20 (2H, m), 1.42 (3H, s, –C–CH₃), 1.20–0.50 (4H, m), 1.01 (3H, s, –C–CH₃), 0.95 (3H, s, –C–CH₃).

(+)-(1R,2R,5S,7R)-3,3-Dichloro-2,8,8-trimethyltricyclo[5.1.1.0^{2,5}]nonan-4-one (**21**) : Reaction of (–)- α -pinene (**15**; 5.0 g, 30 mmol), zinc dust (4 g, 60 mmol) and trichloroacetyl chloride (5.2 ml, 45 mmol) afforded the

dichloroketene adduct (**21**; 3.6 g, 40%) : b.p. 150°/0.5 mm of Hg; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} +30.1^\circ$ (c, 10.0; CHCl₃); ν_{\max} (neat) 2925, 2875, 1800, 1460 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 3.37 (1H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz), 2.50–2.00 (4H, m), 2.00–1.80 (1H, m), 1.54 (3H, s, –C–CH₃), 1.34 (3H, s, –C–CH₃), 1.343 (1H, d, *J* 12.5 Hz), 1.00 (3H, s, –C–CH₃); ^{13}C nmr δ (50.0 MHz) 200.9, 93.1, 55.0, 49.6, 49.3, 39.5, 38.8, 27.9, 27.3, 27.1, 24.0, 21.6.

General procedure for the rearrangement of dichloroketene adducts (16–21) : A three-necked 100 ml RB flask fitted with a reflux condenser, mercury seal and nitrogen inlet was charged with dichloroketene adduct (10 mmol) in dry methanol (10 ml). To it was added freshly prepared sodium methoxide (5 equiv.) solution in methanol through a septum under reflux. The reaction mixture was refluxed for ~30 min. After the complete consumption of the starting material, methanol was removed at reduced pressure and the residue obtained was diluted with water and extracted with ether (2 × 100 ml). The combined ethereal extract was washed, dried and the crude oily product thus obtained was charged on a silica gel column.

1-Methoxy-6-methylbicyclo[4.1.0]hept-7-carboxylic acid methyl esters (22a,b) : Reaction of the ketene adduct (**16**; 290 mg, 0.71 mmol) in methanol (5 ml) with sodium methoxide (5 equiv.) solution in methanol afforded the diastereomeric mixture of cyclopropyl esters (**22a,b**; 202 mg, 73%). Elution of the column with 2% ethyl acetate-hexane afforded the less polar diastereomeric isomer : ν_{\max} (neat) 2915, 1735, 1440, 1210, 1160 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 3.66 (3H, s, –COOCH₃), 3.30 (3H, s, –OCH₃), 2.30–1.10 (8H, series of m), 1.46 (1H, s, –CH–COOCH₃), 1.29 (3H, s, –C–CH₃); ^{13}C nmr δ (25.0 MHz) 171.0, 69.7, 54.0, 50.9, 35.1, 31.5, 27.2, 23.8, 22.1, 21.6, 21.1. Further elution of the column with same eluent gave the more polar diastereomeric isomer : ν_{\max} (neat) 2925, 1730, 1440, 1190, 1160, 1020 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 3.65 (3H, s, –COOCH₃), 3.27 (3H, s, –OCH₃), 2.10–2.00 (2H, m), 1.80–1.60 (2H, m), 1.50–1.00 (4H, m), 1.45 (1H, s), 1.42 (3H, s, –C–CH₃); ^{13}C nmr δ (25.0 MHz) 170.2, 70.1, 54.1, 50.9, 33.5, 32.1, 31.6, 28.0, 21.9, 20.6, 15.3.

1-Methoxy-6-phenylbicyclo[4.1.0]hept-7-carboxylic acid methyl esters (23a,b) : Reaction of **17** (300 mg, 1.1 mmol) with 5 equiv. of sodium methoxide solution in methanol afforded the diastereomeric mixture of cyclopropyl esters (**23a,b**; 214 mg, 74%). Elution with 2% ethyl acetate-hexane afforded the less polar diastereomeric isomer : ν_{\max} (neat) 2910, 1725, 1440, 1220, 1180, 1150 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 7.40–7.10 (5H, m, ArH), 3.75 (3H, s, –COOCH₃), 3.20 (3H, s, –OCH₃), 2.40–1.40 (8H, m), 1.54 (1H, s, –CH–COOCH₃); ^{13}C nmr δ (25.0 MHz) 170.5,

144.4, 128.6 (2C), 128.1 (2C), 126.1, 68.3, 57.8, 51.1, 40.1, 34.0, 29.9, 24.3, 21.4 (2C). Further elution of the column with the same eluent gave the more polar diastereomeric isomer: ν_{\max} (neat) 2900, 2850, 1740, 1700, 1440, 1160 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz), 7.40–7.10 (5H, m, ArH), 3.55 (3H, s, $-\text{COOCH}_3$), 3.21 (3H, s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 2.30–1.10 (9H, series of m); ^{13}C nmr δ (25.0 MHz) 169.2, 140.8, 129.4 (2C), 128.0 (2C), 127.2, 69.9, 54.1, 51.2, 40.8, 36.6, 32.1, 28.9, 21.7, 20.8.

1-Methoxy-5-methylbicyclo[3.1.0]hexane-6-carboxylic acid methyl esters (24a,b): Reaction of 18 (430 mg, 2.23 mmol) with 5 equiv. of sodium methoxide solution in methanol afforded the diastereomeric mixture of cyclopropyl esters (24a,b; 360 mg, 88%): ν_{\max} (neat) 2900, 2850, 1725, 1460, 1440, 1320, 1210, 1170, 1140, 1080, 1040 cm^{-1} .

1-Methoxybicyclo[6.1.0]non-4-en-9-carboxylic acid methyl esters (25a,b): Reaction of 19 (250 mg, 1.14 mmol) with 5 equiv. of sodium methoxide solution in methanol afforded the cyclopropyl esters (25a,b; 120 mg, 50%) after elution from a silica gel column with 2% ethyl acetate-hexane: ν_{\max} (neat) 2900, 1730, 1440, 1360, 1270, 1200 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 5.80–5.60 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$), 3.69 (3H, s, $-\text{COOCH}_3$), 3.19 (3H, s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 2.70–2.50 (1H, m), 2.50–1.90 (6H, m), 1.70–1.10 (3H, m); ^{13}C nmr δ (25.0 MHz) 170.1, 129.9, 129.6, 72.2, 53.9, 51.4, 33.8, 32.7, 30.8, 28.2, 25.8, 23.1.

(1R,3R,5R,7S)-3-Methoxy-5,8,8-trimethyl-tricyclo[5.1.0.0^{3,5}]octane-4-carboxylic acid methyl esters (26a,b): Reaction of 20 (200 mg, 0.81 mmol) with 5 equiv. of sodium methoxide solution in methanol afforded the diastereomeric mixture of cyclopropyl esters (26a,b; 133 mg, 70%). Elution with 2% ethyl acetate-hexane afforded the less polar diastereomeric isomer: ν_{\max} (neat) 2905, 1725, 1440, 1120, 1055, 1020 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 3.65 (3H, s, $-\text{COOCH}_3$), 3.32 (3H, s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 2.57 (1H, dd, J_1 14.54 Hz, J_2 8.8 Hz), 2.23 (1H, dd, J_1 15.2 Hz, J_2 8.6 Hz), 1.80–1.30 (3H, m), 1.18 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 0.97 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 0.80 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 0.60–0.20 (2H, m); ^{13}C nmr δ (25.0 MHz) 170.6, 67.1, 54.3, 51.3, 32.7, 28.0, 27.7, 23.7, 20.8, 19.0, 18.2, 17.2, 16.8, 14.7. Further elution of the column with same eluent gave the more polar diastereomeric isomer: ν_{\max} (neat) 2925, 1730, 1440, 1360, 1325 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 3.66 (3H, s, $-\text{COOCH}_3$), 3.28 (3H, s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 2.60–2.40 (1H, m), 2.20–1.90 (1H, m), 1.74 (1H, s, $-\text{CH}-\text{COOCH}_3$), 1.50–1.20 (2H, m), 1.33 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 1.01 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 0.82 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 0.70–0.30 (2H, m); ^{13}C nmr δ (25.0 MHz) 170.9, 69.3, 54.5, 51.1, 29.0, 27.8 (2C), 27.4, 26.2, 20.3, 18.0, 15.9, 15.1, 13.8.

(1R,2S,4S,6R)-4-Methoxy-2,7,7-trimethyltricyclo-

[4.1.1.0^{2,4}]octane-3-carboxylic acid methyl esters (27a, b): Reaction of the ketene adduct (21; 3.0 g, 12.1 mmol) in methanol (10 ml) with sodium methoxide (5 equiv.) solution in methanol afforded the diastereomeric mixture of cyclopropyl esters (27a,b; 2.0 g, 73%). Elution with 2% ethyl acetate-hexane afforded the less polar diastereomeric isomer: ν_{\max} (neat) 2900, 1718, 1420 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 3.67 (3H, s, $-\text{COOCH}_3$), 3.37 (3H, s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 2.70 (1H, dd, J_1 13.74 Hz, J_2 2.48 Hz), 2.20–1.50 (5H, m), 1.42 (1H, s), 1.24 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 1.23 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 1.01 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$). Further elution of the column with the same eluent afforded the more polar diastereomeric isomer of the cyclopropyl ester: ν_{\max} (neat) 2900, 1715, 1420 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 3.66 (3H, s, $-\text{COOCH}_3$), 3.29 (3H, s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 2.20–1.70 (5H, m), 1.60 (1H, s), 1.34 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 1.27 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 0.99 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), 0.99 (1H, d, J 10.98 Hz); ^{13}C nmr δ (25.0 MHz) 171.9, 63.4, 56.6, 51.6, 45.3, 41.7, 39.8, 37.5, 35.9, 29.9, 26.4, 26.3, 20.2.

General procedure for the DIBAL-H reduction of cyclopropyl esters (22-27): To a solution of cyclopropyl esters (1 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (5 ml) cooled to -78° , DIBAL-H (2 ml of 1.2 M solution in toluene, 2.4 mmol) was added under nitrogen. After the complete consumption of the starting material, the reaction mixture was quenched with saturated ammonium chloride solution and diluted with dichloromethane, washed and dried. Removal of solvent furnished a mixture of cyclopropyl carbinols.

(1-Methoxy-6-methylbicyclo[4.1.0]hept-7-yl)methanol (28): Reaction of the cyclopropyl esters (22a,b; 500 mg, 2.50 mmol) with DIBAL-H afforded the diastereomeric mixture of cyclopropyl carbinols (28; 340 mg, 80%): ν_{\max} (neat) 3350, 2900, 1450, 1090, 1020 cm^{-1} .

(1-Methoxy-6-phenylbicyclo[4.1.0]hept-7-yl)methanol (29): Reaction of the cyclopropyl esters (23a,b; 116 mg, 0.45 mmol) with DIBAL-H afforded the diastereomeric mixture of cyclopropyl carbinols (29; 88 mg, 85%): ν_{\max} (neat) 3350, 2900, 2850, 1600, 1440, 1020 cm^{-1} .

(1-Methoxy-5-methylbicyclo[3.1.0]hex-6-yl)methanol (30): Reaction of the cyclopropyl esters (24a,b; 350 mg, 1.90 mmol) with DIBAL-H afforded the diastereomeric mixture of cyclopropyl carbinols (30; 230 mg, 77%): ν_{\max} (neat) 3350, 2900, 2850, 1450, 1380, 1080, 1020 cm^{-1} .

(1-Methoxy-6-bicyclo[6.1.0]non-4-en-9-yl)methanol (31): Reaction of the cyclopropyl esters (25a,b; 200 mg, 0.95 mmol) with DIBAL-H afforded the diastereomeric mixture of cyclopropyl carbinols (31; 1560 mg, 86%): ν_{\max} (neat) 3350, 2900, 1460, 1250, 1070, 1020 cm^{-1} .

(1R,3R,5R,7S)-(3-Methoxy-5,8,8-trimethyltricyclo[5.1.0.0^{3,5}]octa-4-yl)methanol (32): Reaction of the

cyclopropyl esters (**26a,b**; 200 mg, 0.84 mmol) with DIBAL-H afforded the diastereomeric mixture of cyclopropyl carbinols (**32**, 123 mg, 70%): ν_{\max} (neat) 3350, 2900, 2850, 1440, 1120, 1100 cm^{-1} .

(1*R*,2*S*,4*S*,6*R*)-(4-Methoxy-2,7,7-trimethyltricyclo[4.1.1.0^{2,4}]oct-3-yl)methanol (**33**): Reaction of the cyclopropyl ester (**27a,b**; 1.5 g, 6.0 mmol) with DIBAL-H afforded the diastereomeric mixture of cyclopropyl carbinols (**33**; 900 mg, 72%): ν_{\max} (neat) 3375, 2922, 1460, 1232, 1141, 1049 cm^{-1} .

General procedure for the generation of α -vinyl ketone moiety: To a mixture of cyclopropyl carbinols (1 mmol) in dry pyridine (5 ml) was added methanesulphonyl chloride (1.2 equiv.) at 0°. The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min quenched with water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The reaction mixture was extracted with ether (3 \times 50 ml) and the combined ethereal extract was washed and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. After the removal of the solvent, the crude reaction mixture was again dissolved in ether (50 ml) and treated with a few drops of aq. 35% perchloric acid at 0°. The reaction mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature and stirring continued for 30 min. The reaction mixture was quenched and the ethereal layer was washed and dried. Removal of the solvent and chromatographic separation on a silica gel column by elution with 2% ethyl acetate-hexane furnished the α -vinyl ketone.

2-Methyl-2-vinylcyclohexanone (**34**): Reaction of the carbinols (**28**; 325 mg, 1.91 mmol) with methanesulfonyl chloride (1.2 equiv.) and treatment of the crude reaction mixture with a few drops of 35% aq. perchloric acid afforded the α -vinyl ketone (**34**; 180 mg, 68%): b.p. 120°/1 mm of Hg (Found: C, 78.15; H, 10.18. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ calcd. for: C, 78.21; H, 10.21%); ν_{\max} (neat) 2915, 1710, 1440, 1080 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 5.93 (1H, dd, J_1 17.7 Hz, J_2 10.6 Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.08 (1H, d, J 10.8 Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 4.93 (1H, d, J 17.6 Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 2.60–1.40 (8H, series of m), 1.11 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$); ^{13}C nmr δ (50.0 MHz) 213.1, 142.7, 114.7, 52.1, 39.8, 39.2, 27.6, 23.9, 21.7.

2-Phenyl-2-vinylcyclohexanone (**35**): Reaction of the carbinols (**29**; 116 mg, 0.50 mmol) with methanesulfonyl chloride (1.2 equiv.) and treatment of the crude reaction mixture with a few drops of 35% aq. perchloric acid afforded the α -vinyl ketone (**35**; 67 mg, 65%): b.p. 120°/0.1 mm of Hg (Found: C, 83.75; H, 8.00. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ calcd. for: C, 83.96; H, 8.05%); ν_{\max} (neat) 2900, 2850, 1700, 1440, 1120 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 7.50–7.10 (5H, m, ArH), 6.25 (1H, dd, J_1 17.4 Hz, J_2 10.6 Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.10 (1H, d, J 10.6 Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 4.56 (1H, d, J 17.0 Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 2.80–2.50 (1H, m), 2.50–2.20 (2H, m),

2.10–1.60 (5H, m); ^{13}C nmr δ (25.0 MHz) 212.4, 143.4, 137.8, 129.0 (2C), 127.6 (2C), 127.0, 114.8, 61.0, 40.0, 36.2, 28.0, 21.5.

2-Methyl-2-vinylcyclopentanone (**36**): Reaction of the carbinols (**30**; 220 mg, 1.41 mmol) with methanesulfonyl chloride (1.2 equiv.) and treatment of the crude reaction mixture with a few drops of 35% aq. perchloric acid afforded the volatile product, α -vinyl ketone (**36**; 70 mg, 40%): ν_{\max} (neat) 2900, 2850, 1740, 1450, 920 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 5.78 (1H, dd, J_1 17.4 Hz, J_2 10.8 Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.10 (1H, d, J 10.0 Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.05 (1H, d, J 18.0 Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 2.40–1.70 (6H, m), 1.14 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$); ^{13}C nmr δ (50.0 MHz) 219.7, 140.5, 113.9, 51.8, 36.9, 36.2, 22.2, 18.5.

8-Vinylcyclooct-4-enone (**37**): Reaction of the carbinols (**31**; 108 mg, 0.6 mmol) with methanesulfonyl chloride (1.2 equiv.) and treatment of the crude reaction mixture with a few drops of 35% aq. perchloric acid afforded the α -vinyl ketone (**37**; 70 mg, 72%): b.p. 140/0.1 mm of Hg (Found: C, 80.05; H, 9.27. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ calcd. for: C, 79.95; H, 9.39%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3010, 1710, 920, 740 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 6.00–5.60 (3H, m), 5.10–4.90 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 3.50–3.30 (1H, m), 2.70–2.50 (2H, m), 2.40–2.00 (4H, m), 1.70–1.40 (2H, m); ^{13}C nmr δ (25.0 MHz) 214.4, 138.2, 130.7, 129.9, 115.3, 55.1, 46.5, 31.2, 25.3, 21.9.

(+)-(1*R*,4*R*,6*S*)-4,7,7-Trimethyl-4-vinylbicyclo[4.1.0]hept-3-one (**38**): Reaction of the carbinols (**32**; 270 mg, 1.30 mmol) with methanesulfonyl chloride (1.2 equiv.) and treatment of the crude reaction mixture with a few drops of 35% aq. perchloric acid afforded the α -vinyl ketone (**38**; 156 mg, 78%): b.p. 130–135°/1.0 mm of Hg (Found: C, 80.70; H, 10.14. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ calcd. for: C, 80.85; H, 10.18%); $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} +31^\circ$ (c, 3.78; CHCl_3); ν_{\max} (neat) 2875, 1695, 1445, 905 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 6.14 (1H, dd, J_1 17.4 Hz, J_2 10.8 Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.16 (1H, d, J 10.6 Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.09 (1H, d, J 17.6 Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 2.80–2.60 (1H, m), 2.30–2.10 (2H, m), 1.50–1.30 (1H, m), 1.00–0.90 (2H, m), 1.05 (6H, s, $-\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 0.87 (3H, s, $-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$); ^{13}C nmr δ (25.0 MHz) 215.4, 141.1, 115.1, 49.3, 34.5, 33.9, 27.8, 22.2, 19.2, 18.3, 14.9.

(-)-(1*R*,2*R*,5*R*)-2,6,6-Trimethyl-2-vinylbicyclo[3.1.1]hept-3-one (**39**): Reaction of the carbinols (**33**; 210 mg, 1 mmol) with methane sulphonyl chloride (1.2 equiv.) at 0° and treatment of the crude reaction mixture with a few drops of 35% aq. perchloric acid afforded the α -vinyl ketone (**39**; 65%): b.p. 100°/1.0 mm of Hg (Found: C, 80.51; H, 10.22. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ calcd. for: C, 80.85; H, 10.18%); $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} -120.7^\circ$ (c, 0.81; CHCl_3); ν_{\max} (neat) 2900, 1720, 1640, 1060, 1000, 920 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz) 5.63 (1H, dd, J_1 17.5 Hz, J_2 10.7 Hz, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), 5.03 (1H, d, J 9.95 Hz,

–CH=CH₂), 4.84 (1H, d, *J* 18.24 Hz, –CH=CH₂), 2.80–2.30 (3H, m), 2.20–1.90 (2H, m), 1.60–1.40 (1H, m), 1.36 (3H, s, –C–CH₃), 1.26 (3H, s, –C–CH₃), 0.95 (3H, s, –C–CH₃); ¹³C nmr δ (25.0 MHz) 214.8, 143.3, 113.4, 56.8, 48.7, 44.8, 39.5, 38.7, 31.0, 27.4, 25.5, 23.0.

(+)-(4*R*)-Isopropyl-1-methylcyclohexene (**44**): A mixture of *R*-(+)-limonene (**43**; 63.5 g, 0.46 mmol) and platinum oxide (160 mg) in 95% ethanol (200 ml) was stirred at room temperature under 1 atm. of hydrogen. The reaction was monitored by GC and after the total consumption of the starting material, the solution was filtered and dried over sodium sulfate. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue was distilled to give **44** (55.2 g, 87%): b.p. 55–66°/20 mm; [α]_D +107.9° (*c*, 2.20; CHCl₃); *v*_{max} (neat) 1450, 1380, 1360, 1090, 1055, 798 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (200 MHz) 5.47–5.18 (1H, m, –C=CH), 2.30–1.10 (8H, m), 1.60 (3H, s, –C–CH₃), 0.85 (6H, d, *J* 6 Hz, –CH–CH₃).

(+)-(1*S*,3*R*,6*R*)-8,8-Dichloro-3-isopropyl-6-methylbicyclo[4.2.0]octan-7-one (**45**): This experiment was performed as described in the general procedure for dichloro-ketene addition reaction. Reaction of (+)-*R*-dihydrolimonene (**44**; 4.6 g, 40 mmol) with zinc dust (4 g, 60 mmol) and trichloroacetyl chloride (96.7 ml, 60 mmol) afforded the dichloro-ketene adduct (**45**; 4.8 g, 65%): b.p. 140–145°/1 mm; [α]_D +26.55° (*c*, 3.05; CHCl₃); *v*_{max} (neat) 2900, 2850, 1800 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (200 MHz) 3.70–3.50 (1H, m, O=C–CH–), 2.20–0.70 (8H, series of m), 1.48 (3H, s, –C–CH₃), 0.87 (6H, d, *J* 6.66 Hz, –CHCH₃); ¹³C nmr δ (50.0 MHz) 195.3, 92.1, 58.8, 43.8, 40.3, 34.4, 32.4, 24.8, 23.8, 19.9, 19.3.

(1*S*,3*R*,6*S*)-3-Isopropyl-1-methoxy-6-methylbicyclo[4.1.0]heptan-7-carboxylic acid methyl ester (**46a,b**): This experiment was performed as described in the general procedure for dichloro-ketene adduct rearrangement. Reaction of the ketene adduct (**45**; 3.25 g, 13 mmol) in methanol (10 ml) with sodium methoxide (5 equiv.) solution in methanol afforded the diastereomeric mixture of cyclopropyl esters (**46a,b**; 2.34 g, 75%). Elution with 2% ethyl acetate-hexane afforded the less polar diastereomeric isomer: [α]_D +15.41° (*c*, 5.27; CHCl₃); *v*_{max} (neat) 2900, 2850, 1720, 1460, 1440, 1330, 1200, 1160, 1020, 740 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (200 MHz) 3.64 (3H, s, –COOCH₃), 3.32 (3H, s, –OCH₃), 2.60–1.20 (9H, series of m), 1.28 (3H, s, –C–CH₃), 1.00–0.80 (6H, m, –CH–CH₃); ¹³C nmr δ (25.0 MHz) 171.2, 71.0, 54.3, 51.1, 39.2, 35.6, 32.8, 32.7, 28.6, 27.2, 25.4, 22.1, 19.3 (2C). Further elution of the column afforded the more polar diastereomeric isomer of the cyclopropyl ester (520 mg, 17%): [α]_D +50.86° (*c*, 1.687; CHCl₃); *v*_{max} (neat) 2900, 2850, 1730, 1440, 1360, 1040, 1020 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (200 MHz) 3.64 (3H, s, –COOCH₃), 3.28 (3H,

s, –OCH₃), 2.40–1.20 (9H, series of m), 1.39 (3H, s, –C–CH₃), 1.00–0.70 (6H, m, –CH–(CH₃)₂); ¹³C nmr δ (50.0 MHz), 170.1, 71.5, 54.5, 51.0, 39.3, 35.0, 32.9, 32.2 (2C), 30.7, 25.7, 19.7, 19.5, 15.7.

(1*S*,3*R*,6*S*)-(3-Isopropyl-1-methoxy-6-methylbicyclo[4.1.0]hept-7-yl)methanol (**47a,b**):

Reduction of 46a,b using LAH: To a suspension of lithium aluminum hydride (133 mg, 3.5 mmol) in dry ether (50 ml) cooled in an ice-bath, the ester (**46a,b**; 1.65 g, 6.9 mmol) in ether (10 ml) was added under nitrogen. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h till the starting ester was fully consumed. The reaction mixture was then quenched with a saturated solution of sodium sulfate and extracted with ether (3 × 100 ml). The ethereal layer was dried over sodium sulfate and concentrated to get a crude diastereomeric mixture of alcohols (**47a,b**; 1.09 g, 80%); *v*_{max} (neat) 3350, 2900, 2850, 1460, 1105, 1020, 725 cm⁻¹.

Reduction of 46a,b using DIBAL-H: This experiment was performed as described in the general procedure for DIBAL-H reduction. Reaction of the cyclopropyl esters (**46a,b**; 200 mg, 0.99 mmol) with DIBAL-H afforded the diastereomeric mixture of cyclopropyl carbinols (**47a,b**; 136 mg, 80%).

(+)-(2*S*,5*R*)-5-Isopropyl-2-methyl-2-vinylcyclohexanone (**48**):

Using Py/MsCl method: This experiment was performed as described in the general procedure for α-vinyl ketone preparation. Reaction of the carbinols (**47a,b**; 800 mg, 4 mmol) with methanesulfonyl chloride (1.2 equiv.) and treatment of the crude reaction mixture with a few drops of 35% aq. perchloric acid afforded the α-vinyl ketone (**48**; 567 mg, 78%).

Using TMSI method: Into a 50 ml R.B. flask fitted with a dry nitrogen inlet, septum and mercury seal, was placed sodium iodide (1.5 g, 10 mmol) in dry acetonitrile (10 ml). The cyclopropyl alcohol (**47a,b**; 1 g, 4.7 mmol) in acetonitrile (5 ml) was then added to the mixture at 0° and the same was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. The reaction mixture was diluted with ether (200 ml) and washed successively with sodium thiosulfate solution and brine. Drying and removal of solvent gave a crude product which was charged on a silica gel column. Elution with 2% ethyl acetate-hexane furnished α-vinyl ketone **48** (90%): b.p. 95–100°/1 mm (Found: C, 80.12; H, 11.28. C₁₂H₂₀O calcd. for: C, 79.94; H, 11.18%); [α]_D +60° (*c*, 0.35; CHCl₃); *v*_{max} (neat) 2950, 1705, 1465, 1365, 1180, 910 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (200 MHz) 6.20–6.00 (1H, m, –CH–CH₂), 5.20–4.90 (2H, m, –CH=CH₂), 2.34 (2H, d, *J* 5.32 Hz, –CH₂–CO–), 1.90–1.40 (6H, m), 1.23 (3H, s, –C–CH₃), 0.89 (6H, d, *J* 5.97 Hz, –CH–(CH₃)₂); ¹³C nmr δ (50.0 MHz) 214.0,

142.8, 112.8, 50.5, 45.2, 41.9, 36.7, 31.9, 24.3, 22.5, 19.7, 19.6.

(-)-*(6S)*-3-Isopropyl-6-methyl-6-vinylcyclohex-2-enone (**49**): To a solution of α -vinyl ketone (**48**; 1.0 g, 5.55 mmol) in anhydrous-butanol (10 ml) in a 50 ml three-necked R.B. flask fitted with a reflux condenser, mercury seal, was added selenium dioxide (1.1 g, 10 mmol) in t-butanol (10 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h and then cooled to room temperature. Excess t-butanol was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was charged on a silica gel column. Elution with 2% ethyl acetate-hexane afforded the enone (**49**; 45% yield based on recovered starting material): b.p. 110°/2 mm (Found: C, 81.00; H, 10.23. C₁₂H₁₈O calcd. for: C, 80.85; H, 10.18%); [α]_D -76.08° (c, 0.74; CHCl₃); λ_{\max} 237.0 nm, log ϵ = 4.1196; ν_{\max} (neat) 2965, 2928, 2868, 1670, 1630, 1020, 916, 875, 800 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (200 MHz) 5.84 (1H, dd, J_1 17.49 Hz, J_2 10.74 Hz, -CH=CH₂), 5.85 (1H, s, -C=CH-CO-), 5.20-4.90 (2H, m, -CH=CH₂), 2.50-2.10 (3H, m), 2.10-1.70 (2H, m), 1.19 (3H, s, -C-CH₃), 1.09 (6H, d, J 6.91 Hz, -CH-CH₃); ¹³C nmr δ (50.0 MHz) 202.1, 170.0, 140.9, 122.7, 114.0, 47.5, 35.4, 35.0, 25.0, 22.9, 20.8, 20.6.

(+)- α -Elemene[(+)-*(6S)*-1-Isopropyl-3-isopropylidene-6-methyl-6-vinylcyclohexene (**42**): Into a 25 ml two-necked flask fitted with reflux condenser was suspended freshly cut lithium (5 mg, 0.7 mmol) in dry tetrahydrofuran (5 ml) under nitrogen. 2-Bromopropane (0.5 ml) was injected through a septum. The contents of the flask were sonicated for 10 min for activation. The enone (**49**; 25 mg, 0.14 mmol) in dry tetrahydrofuran (2 ml) was slowly introduced into the flask and the sonication continued for 15 min. The reaction mixture was poured into brine and extracted with ether (2 \times 20 ml). The ethereal layer was dried and concentrated to furnish the crude product **50**.

To a mixture of the above crude product **50** in dry chloroform (10 ml) was added *p*-toluenesulfonyl chloride (cat.) at 0°. The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min, quenched with water and extracted with dichloromethane (2 \times 20 ml). The combined organic solvent was washed, dried and concentrated to a crude product which was filtered through a small silica gel column. Elution with 1% ethyl acetate-hexane on 15% silica gel furnished (+)- α -elemene (**42**; 12 mg, 42% yield based on enone): b.p. 120-130°/7 mm; [α]_D +111.5° (c, 0.65; CHCl₃); ν_{\max} (neat) 3082, 2959, 2924, 2870, 1634, 1460, 1120, 1001, 910, 876, 806 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} 251 nm, log ϵ = 4.998; ¹H nmr δ (200 MHz) 6.37 (1H, s, -C=C-C-CH=C-), 5.78 (1H, dd, J_1 17.24 Hz, J_2 10.73 Hz, -CH=CH₂), 5.10-4.90 (2H, m, -CH=CH₂), 2.40-2.20 (3H, m), 1.81 (3H, s, -C=C-CH₃), 1.73 (3H, s, -C=C-CH₃), 1.70-1.40 (2H, m), 1.18 (3H, s, -C-CH₃), 1.06 (3H,

d, J 6.85 Hz, -CH-CH₃), 1.45 (3H, d, J 6.01 Hz, -CH-CH₃); ¹³C nmr δ (50.0 MHz) 149.7, 146.2, 128.1, 124.5, 119.7, 112.4, 42.2, 37.8, 29.4, 25.3, 24.7, 23.8, 23.1, 20.7, 19.7.

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